
**EVOLVING DEVELOPMENTS IN WILLINGDON COLLEGE
LIBRARY, SANGLI IN DIGITAL ENVIRONMENT**

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Abstract:

The Lord Buddha told that the anything is nothing constant, it continuously going to change its nature. Change is the law of nature. In the physical world human being is the only on the Earth is think, talk and Wright his ideas and solves problems overcome. The dynamic progresses of Information and Communication Technologies (digital) have transformed the old-style notion of libraries in digital Environment. Modern college libraries are additional powerful, active and can impact on their clients excluding the limitations of global limitations. Currently present-day libraries in digital environment are speedily working to digital caring and it can be retrieved globally. With the revolution of digital libraries redesigned their services to borderless world and become lifeblood of the community. Evolving developments in Libraries is use DIGITAL's to accomplish catering digital services, library operations, reader's facilities, standardization and lead of college library activities. The information is evolved from print to digital information have a great Evolving developments in fully mechanisms of the college library organization predominantly the readers, services, facilities and the LIS professionals.

Keywords: College Library, Willingdon College, Sangli, Wdn Library, Evolving Developments, Digital Environment, Library Automation, OPAC, Digital Library.

Introduction:

The Role of college Library:

The College libraries in India have a significant role to play in higher education. Majority of the college libraries do not have appropriate modern facilities & services to meet the needs of users. Their collections are not up-to-date, budgets are their very inadequate and limited, and a large number of them are single. The Wdn college library is well equipped with evolving DIGITAL technology developments for doing modern practices and affords better facilities and services to the offline and

online users of any corner of the World. The library has fully automated with barcode technology, smart barrow cards, OPAC on Web and mobile to cater better facilities of present desires of users. The objectives of this paper are to perceive the current status of Wdn library in evolving developments of DIGITAL environment and understand the future needs and plan of contemporary development.

Willingdon College, Sangli:

With this motto Shri.Vishnushastri Chiplunkar the greatest Marathi writer, with co-operation of his three colleagues

Shri. Bal Gangadhar Tilak, Shri. Gopal Ganesh Agarkar and Mahadeo Ballal Namjoshi opened The New English School in Pune on 1st January, 1880. In 1884 they formed themselves into a corporate body called "The Deccan Education Society" and in 1885 this Society founded, "The Fergusson College," at Pune. With a view to meet the growing demands for higher education in the Western Maharashtra and North Karnataka. The Deccan Education Society, Pune decided to constitute an Arts College in the year 1919. The Life Members of the Society approached the then Governor of Bombay State Lord Willingdon and with his sympathy and support secured recognition for the scheme for an establishment of a College in this region. To appreciate His Excellency Lord Willingdon's interest and help the society decided to name the college as "WILLINGDON COLLEGE".

Wdn College Library, Sangli:

The WDN Library has celebrating centenary Anniversary in the year 2018-2019. Sir Chintamanrao always regarded the college as his own and did everything for it. Shrimant Sir Gangadharrao Ganesh alias Balasaheb Patwardhan presented to the college a splendid collection of books along with cupboards consisting 4797 books. This was the foundation of the Library Department and in deference of Sir Gangadharrao Patwardhan's wishes this library has been named after his late wife, "Shrimant Saubhagyawati Umabaisaheb Patwardhan Library."

The library has big donated collection is near about 30000 consists of The Miraj , Sangli State library and HH Rajesaheb Chintamanrao Patwardhan personal collections. The library has subscribed 116 National and International journals and magazines, 12 newspapers and 6300 e-journals and 138500 e-books under N-List Program of INFLIBNET, Ahmedabad.

Sr. No.	Title	No. of Volumes	No. of Titles	Total Cost
1	Senior College	89722	68070	9,34,6768.09
2	UGC Grant	10393	7390	2,89,397.00
3	Sangli State Library	4623	4623	-
4	Miraj State Library	4797	4797	-
5	H.H. Rajesaheb personal Collection	4955	4955	-
6	Total Books	125203	83882	10000734.00
7	Periodicals/Journals	119	119	50,000.00
8	Bound Volumes	7500	7500	-
9	Theses	30	30	-
10	Newspapers	12	12	-
11	Non-Print Material (e-Resources CD's/DVD's)	177		7500.00
12	Manuscripts	129	129	-

Table-1. Library Collection

Evolving Developments in WDN College Library in Digital Environment:

Wdn college library has carrying many evolving developments related to DIGITAL . The college libraries are going to change their role of operation,
Prof. D. D. Waghmare

management and facilities according to the evolving developments of DIGITAL and information revolution. The continuously changing DIGITAL technology and its impact on the college library management by attaining innovative developments of

DIGITAL environment. The information is changed from print to non-print, digital formats due to DIGITAL development. The working and functions of academic libraries have changing from manual to computerize and digital because of DIGITAL revolution. Today College libraries are used many DIGITAL related technology, like barcode, Quadra core, e-library, digital library, web-OPAC, Mobile-OPAC, cloud computing, RFID technology, Consortia, etc. in the operation of library. The Wdn library acquired library automation, barcode system, digital library, E-library, and online learning resources to provide better library facilities to the users.

Evolving Developments in library Facilities and Services:

The WDN library has attained new DIGITAL technologies according to the

changing needs of users. The library has fully computerized with barcode facility by purchasing Vidyasagar library management software. The library has provides the new DIGITAL related services and facilities like library website, OPAC, N-List program and internet facility by establishing UGC NRC Centre in the library. The library has organized orientation program related to DIGITAL related services and facilities for the new coming readers. The library has developed E-library and available membership of N-list program for the readers. The library has also provided Mobile OPAC services to the readers by developing ‘VidysagarWhatsApp’ facility and it is availed by providing ID’s and PW’s to users. The library has developed the following DIGITAL related facilities and services to the readers-

Sr. No.	Facilities	Particulars
1	OPAC	On Line Public Access Catalogue available for users
1	Electronic Resource Management package for e-journals	• Available through N-LIST INFLIBNET
2	Library Website	•Dedicated web page on the college website
3	In-house/remote access to e-publications	• Available through N-LIST INFLIBNET
4	Library Automation	• Services fully automated (Bar Code)
5	Total number of computers for public access	• 4 Computers
6	Internet band width/ speed	• 22 Mbps (Lease line- Reliance)
7	Institutional Repository	• On College Intranet (Server)
8	Participation in Resource sharing networks/consortia (like N-LIST INFLIBNET)	• N-LIST INFLIBNET Member

Table-2.Facilities

Special Libraries:

Special Libraries for science have been set-up in the Departments of Biotechnology, Chemistry, Botany, Computer Science, Electronics, Mathematics, Physics and Statistics. Special Libraries for Social Sciences & humanities have been set-up in the Departments of History, Economics, Geography, Hindi, English and Marathi, etc. These libraries are run by the Student Secretaries of the concerned departments under the guidance of the concerned Heads of Departments.

Library Automation:

The Wdn library has computerized by **Vidysagar** library management software with multilingual and multiuser facility. All activities in the library are done through computer & internet based only. All the books have the bar-code stickers. Students issued smart barrow Cards with Bar-code facility. There are ten computers having LAN & high speed internet facility in the library. Out of these one is for library users i.e. for the students and teachers to search the book through OPAC (Online Public Access Catalogue) in the library and through web-OPAC and mobile-OPAC are accessed from outside the library. The job of circulation of information/books, indexing, reports generation, statistics and section wise works are computerized. Due to DIGITAL in the library functions and services are become faster and easier due to computerization. There is an E-Library in the Library to access and downloads e-books, e-newspapers and e-journals & it gives online reading facility to students in the library.

Library Orientation Program:

It plays a vigorous part in growing the utilization of the library holding

competitive resources. At the opening of every academic year this library orientation by PPT presentation is providing through the goal to present new students to different kinds of competitive exam resources, records, plans of the library and being of several gears to feat these information resources to the extreme. Later orientation program they are requested for the library appointment to realize its different units.

Online Resources Services:

In the present DIGITAL atmosphere students choose internet to hunt the required information of competitive exams. Motives actualities unlike treasured resources are accessible on net. Thus, now readers are providing thru allowed internet surfing facility for educational needs merely below work administration. Library employees also assist them for searching the necessary information competently. Ten client PCs are ardent for accessing the digital resources of various fields of study and competitive exams. Library is too displayed a list of beneficial webs sites on employ, career, open e-books, permitted e-journals, encyclopedias, etc. in related to competitive exams displaying at the notice boards and website

Library Website:

Library has a separate Linkage on the College website (willingdoncollege.in). The Website of the college is <http://www.willingdoncollege.in>. A client can search/access every book of the library sitting at home from any corner of the world through Web-OPAC. The E-Mail address of the library is wdnlibrary@gmail.com Users can interact with the library staff through the e-mail for their short term and long term

information queries and library services.

OPAC:

Library has OPAC facility in the Library with on separate computer for students and teachers. The Web –OPAC Facility is on the college website and it is also provided outside the library through IDs and PWs from any corner of the World. There are three types of OPACs are used in the Wdn library, one is OPAC, it is used in library counter for all users on a desktop with LAN facility.

Web-OPAC:

The library has fully computerized with barcode and OPAC facility. Through this library software library has given Web –OPAC online facility to the students and teachers.

Mobile OPAC (WhatsApp):

The library has provided Mobile OPAC services to the readers by developing ‘Vidysagar’ WhatsApp facility. The facilities are used on the 4G mobile phone to download Vidyasagar App from google play store and installed it by providing IDS and PWs. They have following features-

Internet Facilities through UGC NRC Centre: Library has introduced internet facility to all the through UGC NRC Centre in the study room from time 8.30am to 6.00 pm. Average daily 25 students were used the internet access for their study proposes.

E-Pathashala for PG: INFLIBNET Centre has provided HRD Ministry project to provide PG syllabus e-material like Text notes, video lecturers and objectives practices for post graduate students. The E-pathashala training will provide to the students from

Institutional Repository: Library has College Magazines, Annual Reports,

Readers can gives feedbacks

Theses and books are maintained in a Separate section.

Content management system for e-learning-Participation in Resource sharing networks/consortia (like Infflibnet)

Barcode Facility: Library has Barcode facility in the library. Each book has barcoded with barcode sticker and is useful for easy circulation and maintains book records. There is a bacode machine for scan of barcodes in the library operations.

Conclusion:

The WDN Library Sangli has fully automated with Barcode, OPAC, Web-OPAC, Mob-OPAC, N-List Program facility. The library has provided internet, E-library, digital Library, to the readers by maintaining the UGC NRC Centre in the library. The library has observed that the readers are access of DIGITAL related facilities in their studies. The library has subscribed N-List program of INFLIBNET, Ahmedabad. The library has better infrastructure facilities with 10 computers with LAN and internet facilities. The library has organized library orientation program for the readers related to DIGITAL technologies. The WDN library is well equipped and fully developed with latest DIGITAL facilities and the college has recently awarded ‘A’ grade in NAAC Re-Accreditation by NAAC, Bangalore.

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